

What is the Hawai'i Climate Data Portal (HCDP)

- **A Place** to get climate data and information
- **A Tool** that allows us to explore the past, monitor the present, and project the future
- **A Portal** to other places and data sources
- **An Opportunity** to learn, to education, to network, and to share

<https://hawaii.edu/hcdp>

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Visualize Data

Visualize available climate data in the portal.

Customize a Map

Download map

Name	Station ID	Island
PunaluuRainGagealt	884.4	O'ahu
SCHOFIELD BARRACKS	898	O'ahu
Poamoho Exp Farm	855.3	O'ahu
DILLINGHAM	843.7	O'ahu
MakahaRainGage	842.1	O'ahu
Waihee Pump	839.8	O'ahu
WAIHAOLE STREAM NEAR KAHALUU 2N	837.12	O'ahu
Palisades	835.2	O'ahu
Waiawa CF	834.13	O'ahu
SCHOFIELD EAST	828	O'ahu
Waipio	824.2	O'ahu
Milliani	820.6	O'ahu
WHEELER ARMY AIR FIELD 810.1	810.1	O'ahu
WAIANA E VALLEY	803.2	O'ahu
Waimanalo Nonokio	795.3	O'ahu
BELLOWS AFS AT WAIMANALO	793.2	O'ahu

Station Metadata	
SKN (Station ID)	884.4
Name	PunaluuRainGagealt
Observer	USGS
Network	USGS
Island	O'ahu
Elevation (m)	73.15
Latitude	21.56
Longitude	-157.9
NWS ID	PNSH1
NESDIS ID	DD989652
Value	120.39

Get Station Meta Data

Adjustable time series plots Daily or monthly

